

Chapter 2 from LEVITATE project deliverable D3.1

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2 A review of taxonomies

This chapter reviews studies that give an overview of potential impacts of connected and automated transport systems. The studies are reviewed in chronological order and for each study a list is made of the impacts it discusses and the relationships between these impacts. No single study includes all potential impacts of CATS. A consolidated list has been developed by including all impacts that are mentioned in at least one of the studies reviewed.

While connected and automated transport systems are developing fast, they have still not been implemented to such an extent that one can evaluate their impacts by means of, for example, before-and-after studies. Therefore, all the studies discussed in this chapter discuss potential impacts only. Which of the potential impacts that will turn into real impacts, depends on the level of implementation of CATS and on policy made to ensure that the implementation of CATS takes place in a way that will ensure maximum benefits of the technology. The studies reviewed in this chapter include only those that list potential impacts of CATS or discuss these in general terms, not studies describing methods that can be used to evaluate specific impacts. Studies of evaluation methods will be reviewed in deliverable D3.2.

2.1 Fagnant and Kockelman 2015

Fagnant and Kockelman (2015) discuss potential impacts of automated vehicles under the following headings:

1. Safety
2. Congestion (travel time)
3. Fuel consumption
4. Vehicle emissions
5. Mobility among those without a driving license
6. Smart parking solutions
7. Savings in freight transport
8. No need for truck drivers
9. Change in distance travelled per vehicle
10. Change in vehicle ownership
11. Induced travel demand
12. Change in car ownership cost

Some of these impacts are related to each other. Thus, an expected reduction in congestion will lead to reduce fuel consumption which in turn reduces vehicle emissions. Reduction in congestion means reduction in travel time, which may induce new travel demand (a rebound effect). The causal chain can be modelled as follows:

The rebound effect is shown by a curved arrow. It counteracts the primary effect, i.e. all else equal induced travel increases congestion, thus reducing the initial effect of automated vehicles in terms of reducing congestion.

There is, in a similar manner, a relationship between savings in freight transport and no need for truck drivers, as the elimination of drivers is one of the main contributing factors to the savings. In addition, platooning of vehicles reduces fuel consumption and may reduce travel time.

According to Fagnant and Kockelman, a 90 % implementation rate for automated vehicles can increase road capacity by 80 %. They further note that the long-term demand elasticity of urban vehicle kilometres of travel with respect to lane-kilometres supplied is 0.74. Thus, as a rough estimate, the rebound effect will eliminate 74 % of the 80 % increase in road capacity, leaving a net gain of 21 %. (a rebound effect of 74 % means that 26 % of the primary effect remains; thus when road capacity increases by 1 %, the increase in traffic means that it only increase by 0.26%. Repeating these estimates percent-by-percent up to 80 % shows that the net increase in road capacity will be just 21 %). Fagnant and Kockelman perform a cost-benefit analysis including safety effects, reduced congestion and parking savings on the benefit side and the added purchase price of a vehicle on the cost side. The assumptions made in this analysis are quite simple and rest on an interpretation of available studies, not a detailed modelling or simulation of effects.

2.2 Hörl, Ciari and Axhausen 2016

Hörl, Ciari and Axhausen (2016) review potential impacts of automated vehicles. They list potential impacts under the following headlines:

1. Mobility
 - a. Increase in road capacity as a result of:
 - i. Connected vehicles
 - ii. Fewer delays as a result of fewer accidents
 - iii. Improved infrastructure
 - b. Induced travel demand
2. City planning
 - a. Changes in infrastructure
 - i. Reduced need for parking spaces
 - ii. Increased need for spaces for dropping off and picking up people
 - iii. Charging stations for electric vehicles
 - b. Changes in accessibility
 - i. Increased urban sprawl

- c. Changes in emissions
 - i. Less CO2 emissions
 - ii. Less noise (automated vehicles are assumed to be electric)
- 3. Car industry
 - a. Production and business model
 - b. Law, liability and insurance
- 4. Work organization
- 5. User profiles
- 6. Delivery of goods
- 7. Price

The first item is identical to items covered by Fagnant and Kockelman (2015). In both studies, road capacity is expected to increase, and induced demand is expected to arise. Hörl, Ciari and Axhausen identify three mechanisms producing an increase in road capacity: the fact that automated vehicles will be connected and thus travel at shorter headways with a uniform speed; the reduced probability of delays caused by accidents, as there is expected to be fewer accidents; finally, improved infrastructure enabling vehicle-to-infrastructure communication to optimise route choice, lane use or driving speed.

When modelling the changes in road capacity associated with different levels of implementation of CATS, it is the net result that counts. It is not necessary to model the three mechanisms explicitly, but the direct effect and rebound effect (induced travel demand) should be modelled explicitly and quantified.

Hörl, Ciari and Axhausen expect increased urban sprawl, but environmental benefits in terms of reduced CO2 emissions and less noise. The latter two impacts arise principally because they assume that automated vehicles will be electric. This, of course, will increase electricity consumption and the net impact on the environment depends on how electricity and electric vehicles are produced. At this point, it is regarded as outside the scope of LEVITATE to assess environmental impacts of the production of electricity or electric vehicles. Users of the policy support tool will be informed that only emissions from driving are included, not the full life-cycle emissions.

The car industry may change its business model when automated vehicles become widespread. Rather than just producing the cars, vehicle manufacturers may see additional business opportunities in car-sharing schemes or taxi services such as Uber and Lyft. The additional costs of offering these services will be minimal once full automation is reached, as there will be no need for a driver.

The absence of a driver may change legislation regarding legal responsibility for accidents. Today, road users are held responsible for accidents; yet not without some important exceptions. In the United States vehicle recalls are not uncommon. A recall means that car manufacturers ask car owners to bring the car back to the factory to correct a malfunction or design failure made by the manufacturer. This kind of product liability will probably have to be extended considerably once vehicles become automated.

Work organisation has to do with increased flexibility in working hours. The Internet already facilitates working from home in many occupations; automated vehicles will make working while commuting easier. This may in turn lead to increased tolerance of longer commutes and thus urban sprawling.

Hörl, Ciari and Axhausen expect automated vehicles to be used as shared vehicles. This is somewhat inconsistent with the expectation of increased urban sprawl, at least if that takes the form of single family houses with a garden, US suburban style. This type of land use is very low density and does not easily lend itself to service by means of public transport or even shared private vehicles, although vehicle sharing may work for specific trip purposes (e.g. children all going to the same school). On the other hand, if urban sprawl takes the form of higher density developments, it may be easier to share the use of automated vehicles.

Delivery of goods is expected to become cheaper and need less manpower. Finally, Hörl, Ciari and Axhausen expect automated vehicles to be at least initially more expensive than conventional vehicles.

2.3 Chan 2017

Chan (2017) discusses potential impacts of automated driving systems and lists the following impacts:

1. Vehicle user impacts
 - a. Fewer accidents
 - b. More comfortable and less stressful trips
 - c. Enhanced mobility for children, the disabled, etc.
 - d. More productive trips (i.e. possibility of working)
 - e. A more attractive mode of transport
 - f. Less demanding or unnecessary vehicle ownership
 - g. Automated event handling in case of vehicle failure
2. Transport system impacts
 - a. Reduced congestion
 - b. More effective real-time navigation, dynamic routing
 - c. More accessible, reliable and flexible shared rides
 - d. Fewer vehicles on the road as a result of ride sharing
 - e. More efficient infrastructure
 - f. More affordable mobility services for public agencies
 - g. Improved economic returns for private investors
 - h. Savings in parking areas or other road constructions
3. Societal impacts
 - a. Less need for customized mobility services for those with special needs
 - b. Greater incentive to shift from owning to sharing cars
 - c. No driver shortage
 - d. Reduced insurance and related ownership costs
 - e. Reduced accident rates
 - f. More environmentally friendly vehicles and infrastructure
 - g. Increasing quality of transport services with respect to safety, reliability, security and productivity

Many of the items on this list of impacts were also listed by Fagnant and Kockelman (2015) and by Hörl, Ciari and Axhausen (2016). The list has a few redundancies. Thus, impact 1a may be seen as identical to 3e, unless 1a applies to individual drivers and 3e to the aggregate level. Impacts 1c and 3a are also, if not identical, then at least overlapping to a great degree. Impacts 1f and 3b seem to be almost the same. Impacts 3d and 3e are really two aspects of the same impact.

Some of the impacts are not discussed in further detail and it is not entirely clear how they arise or manifest themselves. Impact 2g, improved economic returns for private investors belongs to this category.

It is nevertheless clear that some of the impacts listed are included on all lists of potential impacts of CATS, as will be seen in subsequent sections. This applies to fewer accidents, reduced congestion, and reduced environmental effects of transport. Quite a few lists of impacts also include less need for parking areas.

Chan does not discuss the relationships between the impacts or attempt to form a causal diagram for them.

2.4 Milakis, van Arem and van Wee 2017

Milakis, van Arem and van Wee (2017) give a very comprehensive review of potential impacts of automated driving and discuss each of the impacts in some detail. They propose a distinction between first-order, second-order and third-order impacts, based on the model shown in Figure 1 (copied from their paper).

At the centre of the model is the vehicle automation technology. Its use in the transport system generates at first impacts that are directly noticed by road users, shown in the light blue circle. Outside of that are second-order impacts, relating to, for example, vehicle ownership rates and employment. Finally, the outermost circle identifies third-order impacts. Milakis et al. list the following first-, second- and third-order impacts:

Figure 1 The ripple model of the effects of automated vehicles. Source: Milakis, van Arem and van Wee (2017)

1. First-order impacts
 - a. Travel cost
 - i. Fixed cost of automated vehicles
 - ii. Travel comfort
 - iii. Travel time
 - iv. Value of travel time
 - b. Road capacity
 - i. Highway capacity
 - ii. Intersection capacity
 - c. Travel choices
 - i. Vehicle kilometres travelled
2. Second-order impacts
 - a. Vehicle ownership
 - b. Location choices and land use
 - c. Transport infrastructure
3. Third-order impacts
 - a. Energy consumption and air pollution
 - i. Fuel efficiency
 - ii. Energy consumption (long term)
 - iii. Emissions
 - iv. Air pollution
 - b. Safety
 - c. Social equity
 - d. Economy
 - e. Public health

It is not made clear how impacts were sorted into the three main groups. Milakis, van Arem and van Wee review a large number of studies that have tried to assess these impacts. Some impacts are related to each other or nested within each other. Thus, as indicated, changes in travel cost (i.e. the generalised cost of travel) are the sum of the costs of owning and operating vehicles and the value of travel time. One should possibly also add part of the cost of accidents, but in the taxonomy proposed by Milakis et al. accidents belong to the third-order effects.

Milakis et al. survey the literature and indicate the likely sign of each impact. The fixed costs of automated vehicles are expected to be higher than for manually operated vehicles. Travel time is expected to be reduced. The signs of the impacts on travel comfort and the value of travel time are listed as indeterminate by Milakis et al., meaning that they do not indicate whether impacts will be favourable or unfavourable. Most studies that have tried to simulate the effects of CATS assume that the value of travel time will be reduced. Road capacity and vehicle kilometres of travel are both expected to increase, meaning that the rebound effect on congestion from increased vehicle kilometres is not expected to eliminate the benefits of increased road capacity.

Vehicle ownership is expected to decline, and shared vehicles (or shared use of them) will replace many individually owned vehicles. Effects on location choice and land use are indeterminate. The need for parking space is expected to decline. Note that Milakis et al. discuss this effect under the heading of transport infrastructure, whereas Hörl, Ciari and Axhausen discussed it under the heading of city planning.

Fuel efficiency is expected to increase, and emissions expected to reduce. A transition to electric vehicles will further increase energy efficiency and reduce air pollution. Safety is expected to increase, but it is noted that the gains in safety can be limited by behavioural adaptation, cyberattacks and software limitations. Regarding social equity, economy and public health, little is known, but better access to transport for those who cannot drive can be seen as a gain in equity.

2.5 Herrmann, Brenner and Stadler 2018

Herrmann, Brenner and Stadler (2018) is a book of 445 pages dealing with autonomous driving. It has a popular science style, but covers many aspects of the introduction of CATS and its potential impacts. The following list of impacts are discussed in the book:

1. Road capacity (expected to increase)
2. Fuel economy (expected to improve)
3. Vehicle operating costs (expected to decrease)
4. Road safety (expected to improve)
5. Use of in-vehicle time (time liberated for use to work, entertainment, etc)
6. Land use (less need for parking space)
7. Dynamic routing (through interaction with intelligent infrastructure)
8. Transition to electric cars (may be faster)
9. Access to mobility (increased for people without a driving licence)

One aspect of the transition to automated driving discussed in this book is the ongoing competition between technology companies and car manufacturers concerning the development of fully autonomous cars. Technology companies, like Google, have taken the step straight to SAE level 5 automated vehicles, skipping the intermediate stages of 2, 3 and 4. The book argues that it is still not entirely clear who will win the competition, but that skipping the intermediate stages of automation is attractive, because there is a worry that some intermediate levels, in particular SAE level 3, will not function well. At SAE level 3, the car is autonomous, but only in defined operational domains. An operational domain could be defined in terms of, for example, the type of road (motorways only), or a certain range of environmental conditions in which the autonomous system functions. Sensors, for example, may have degraded function in rain, snow, or fog. In these conditions the driver may be requested to take over control of the vehicle.

If the car has been in autonomous mode for some time, the driver may be ill-prepared to take over control when asked to do so. This has been shown in many simulator studies as well as on-road studies (Eriksson and Stanton 2018). Some car manufacturers have established formal cooperation with technology companies in developing automated cars, but the possibility still exists that there will be two parallel paths in the transition to automated driving – one that may be called “evolutionary” and will proceed step-by-step through a number of levels, and one that may be called “disruptive” and will go straight for the highest level of automation. In principle, government can influence the course technological innovation takes, e.g. by indicating that SAE level 3 cars will not be approved for use on public roads.

When developing models for predicting the impacts of CATS, it is definitely most convenient to assume that the vehicles are at the highest level of automation, and that the only aspect of the transition to full automation considered is changes in the market

penetration rate of fully automated vehicles. It is recognised, however, that this perspective is too narrow to adequately model all impacts of CATS. As an example, stand-alone technologies like cooperative intelligent cruise control, enabling vehicles to form platoons, may become available and used before full automation of all driving functions has been accomplished. It is then relevant to assess the impacts of platooning separately. Other specific technologies may also require separate impact assessments.

2.6 Hibberd et al. 2018

The report by Hibberd et al. (2018; 21 authors listed) is a deliverable from the ongoing L3Pilot project, a Horizon 2020 project with Volkswagen as coordinator. This project will test SAE level 3 automation systems in real traffic. It is part of the ongoing technological development in addition to being a research project.

Like other recent or ongoing projects, L3Pilot has developed a list of potential impacts of automated driving. An interesting aspect of the list is that it goes further than other lists in specifying indicators to measure the various impacts. Some of these indicators are listed below for the most important impacts discussed by the L3Pilot project:

1. System technical performance
 - a. Vehicle data on system status
2. Driver behavior
 - a. Vehicle data on lateral and longitudinal acceleration, lane position, etc
3. Interaction with other road users
 - a. Vehicle data on time headway and time to collision
4. Impact on safety
 - a. Simulated frequency of accidents
5. Environmental impacts
 - a. Average fuel consumption per vehicle
6. Travel behavior (exposure)
 - a. Number of trips per time unit; number of times parking; distribution of trip duration
7. Socio-economic impacts
 - a. Several indicators based both on vehicle data and questionnaires

It is interesting to note that surrogate safety measures, like time headway and time to collision are assumed to be recorded by the vehicle. If it can be assumed that automated vehicles will have this capability, then objective data on safety indicators can be collected and used to monitor the safety performance of automated vehicles. A dilemma arises because current vehicles are normally not equipped to collect these data, although that is possible without automation. Thus, currently available data on, for example, the frequency of short headways or short times to collision, are incomplete; at best sample data based on video recordings are available. It is likely that once such data are collected on a routine basis, the frequency of short headways or short times to collision will be found to be higher than hitherto believed, suggesting – if changes in these indicators are used to evaluate changes in road safety – that automated vehicles are associated with a deterioration of safety, when in fact it is only the reporting of safety indicators that has become more systematic and complete.

It is also interesting to note that the simulated frequency of accidents is proposed as indicator or safety effect. While simulating accidents may be possible, it is easier to

simulate surrogate events, involving the loss of safety margins. Surrogate events are vastly more frequent than accidents. Once automated cars start being used in traffic, naturalistic driving data could be a source of the frequency both of accidents and surrogate events.

Hibberd et al. present a figure modelling the effects of SAE level 3 automated vehicles. The figure is reproduced below as Figure 2.

The figure is impressive in its detail and the number of links indicated between the variables. The final impacts are listed to the right. Intermediate impacts are indicated between the leftmost and rightmost columns. For consistency, the variables to the left should be those that generate impacts, i.e. independent variables, in this case the performance capabilities of SAE level 3 automated vehicles. This principle is not fully adhered to in the Figure. Nevertheless, the figure is the most complete identification of potential impacts of CATS found in the studies that have been reviewed. It may thus serve as a model for developing a similar causal diagram in LEVITATE.

2.7 Hoadley et al. 2018

Hoadley (2018), on behalf of the Polis traffic efficiency and mobility working group, has written a paper discussing potential impacts for cities and regions of automated vehicles. The following potential impacts are identified:

1. Travel demand (increase expected)
2. Modal split of travel (less cycling, walking and public transport expected)
3. Space used for parking (reduction expected)
4. Urban sprawl (increase expected)
5. Commuting distance (increase expected)
6. Accessibility to transport (increase for those with low accessibility)
7. Inequality in transport (may increase)
8. Employment (may change)
9. Value of time (may become lower as it can be spent on productive things)
10. Public finances (may be weakened)
11. Road safety (may improve)
12. Utilisation of road space (may increase outside cities)
13. Data for traffic management (detailed data may become available)

The report notes that several of the potential impacts of automated vehicles are not obviously favourable. In particular, an increase in vehicle kilometres and a reduction of walking and cycling goes against current political objectives in many cities. It is, however, possible to counteract such a development by means of, for example, road pricing. With respect to safety benefits, the report notes that:

“Achieving road safety benefits presumes that systems are always on, always fully operational and will “fail safe”. This is a big ask: In 2017, connected cars can be hacked; transport booking systems overbooked; fleet management systems can fail; power and communications systems have outages; components fail; and navigation guidance is not infallible.”

Figure 2 Impacts of automated driving. Source: Hibberd et al 2018, figure 2.5

These observations are correct. Automated systems need to have a very high reliability in order to perform better than human drivers. However, it should not be forgotten that human operators sometimes voluntarily choose to degrade their performance and erode their safety margins by drinking and driving, speeding, tailgating, or otherwise adopting a behaviour that involves an avoidable risk. Speeding, drinking and driving, and non-use of seat belts contribute to about 30-40 % of all traffic fatalities, and automated vehicles may eliminate this contribution.

2.8 Innamaa et al. 2018

Innamaa et al. (2018; 7 authors) present an impact assessment framework for automated road transport, based on a trilateral cooperative project involving the EU, the USA and Japan. The potential impacts of CATS are presented in a figure, which is reproduced below as Figure 3.

Figure 3 Potential impacts of connected and automated transport systems. Source: Innamaa et al. 2018, Figure 1

The list of impacts includes those that have been identified in other recent overviews. A distinction is made between two dimensions: (1) The time dimension (X-axis) and (2) the geographic scale of impacts. Safety impacts have been classified as an impact at the person/vehicle level occurring within a time-frame of seconds. This should probably not be interpreted as suggesting that safety impacts cannot be observed at, for example, the

regional or national levels, or that safety impacts disappear after a few seconds. Safety impacts are likely to be observable at the national level and for a period of many years. The idea of sorting impacts in groups is attractive, but there is no consensus in the reviewed papers about how to do it. Milakis et al. (2017) discuss first-, second- and third order impacts. Hibberd et al. (2018) identify impacts at four stages of a causal chain, where the stages are partly in a logical order, partly in a chronological order. Finally, Innamaa et al. (2018) use geographic and temporal extension as sorting dimensions. Rather than finding the “correct” way to classify impacts, it is important to ensure that a taxonomy of potential impacts is:

1. Complete, i.e. includes all impacts that have been identified in at least one study
2. Operational, i.e. suggests at least one indicator of an impact intended to measure it.

According to these criteria, the review of Innamaa et al. (2018) is useful by listing impacts and indicators of them in an Appendix. The Appendix runs to five pages. For illustration, the main headings and a few selected indicators are listed for each of the impacts included:

1. Use of automated driving
 - a. Number of times the driver takes over control per 1000 km
 - b. Minimum time used to take over control
2. Vehicle operations
 - a. Mean speed and speed variation
 - b. Mean and minimum time headway to vehicle in front
3. Safety
 - a. Number of accidents per 100 million km
 - b. Number of conflicts with time to collision below a set value per 100 million km
 - c. Proportion of time with time to collision less than a set value
4. Energy consumption and environment
 - a. Energy consumption in kWh per year
 - b. Emissions of local air pollution
5. Personal mobility
 - a. Number of trips made per day
 - b. Waiting time for vehicle (in shared mobility schemes)
 - c. Number of new trips made per year
6. Travel behaviour
 - a. Total kilometres travelled in a region
 - b. Share of transport modes
 - c. Network level journey time per week
7. Network efficiency
 - a. Road capacity at design speed
 - b. Peak period travel time along a route
8. Asset management
 - a. V2I infrastructure for automation
 - b. Pavement condition (ruts and evenness)
9. Costs
 - a. Cost of buying automated vehicle
 - b. Operating costs of automated vehicle
10. Public health

- a. Population exposed to air pollution
- b. Modal share of active transport (walking or cycling)
- 11. Land use
 - a. Density of housing
 - b. Parking area
 - c. Space needed for roads
- 12. Economic impact
 - a. Work time gained due to working while travelling
 - b. Number of jobs lost to automation
 - c. Share of household budget spent on transport

These are just a few of the indicators listed. The final choice of indicators will be influenced by their analytic tractability, i.e. how well they lend themselves to simulation or other forecasting techniques that will be used in LEVITATE.

2.9 Kockelman and Boyles 2018

Kockelman and Boyles (2018) have edited a book of about 450 pages presenting current knowledge about impacts of connected and automated transport systems. The list of (most) chapters in the book gives an overview of the type of impacts it covers:

1. Identification of CAV (connected and automated vehicles) technologies
2. Operational domains of CAVs
3. Estimating the safety benefits of CAV technologies
4. CAV applications pertaining to traffic management operations
5. Inertial measurement data with traffic flow models for traffic monitoring
6. Legal environment of self-driving vehicles with CAVs
7. Traffic models for automated vehicles
8. MOVES emission modelling
9. Application of traffic models
10. Design and implementation of shared autonomous vehicle system
11. Making the most of curb spaces in a world of shared autonomous vehicles
12. Benefit-cost analysis

Subsections in the chapters show that the impacts considered are: safety, mobility, connectivity, sustainability, land use, and economic impacts. Extensive simulations have been performed in order to predict these impacts. The results of these simulations may serve as input for developing functional relationships relating the effects of CATS to their level of implementation.

The report briefly discusses other impacts of CATS and notes, for example, that the need for traffic police is likely to be reduced. Thus, one may foresee impacts on employment in at least three occupations: (1) professional drivers, who will no longer be needed when all vehicles are fully automated and autonomous; (2) garage and service station personnel, as fewer accidents will reduce the need for repairs and a transition to electric vehicles eliminates (or strongly reduces) the need for fuel stations (it seems reasonable to assume that recharging of electric vehicles can be done by owners without the need for professional personnel); (3) traffic police, as automated vehicles will presumably not commit traffic violations. Overall, therefore, CATS is likely to reduce employment in the transport sector.

2.10 Pribyl et al. 2018

Pribyl et al. (2018; 13 authors in total) is a deliverable from the MAVEN project (MAVEN = Managing Automated Vehicles Enhances Network) which discusses potential impacts of CATS. The report mentions the following potential impacts of CATS:

1. Efficiency of transport
2. Road safety
3. Traffic flow
4. Vehicle emissions
5. Accessibility
6. Law, liability and insurance
7. Work organisation

These potential impacts are not discussed in great detail, but the report is clear about the need for developing a policy to regulate and manage the introduction of CATS to ensure that desirable impacts are obtained and unwanted feedback impacts avoided.

2.11 Position papers on safety by FERSI and ITF

In addition to the studies quoted above, it is worth mentioning two position papers on road safety impacts of automated vehicles published in 2018 by FERSI and ITF.

The FERSI paper proposes ten principles for ensuring that automation will bring about enhanced road safety. The paper notes that pilot versions of automated vehicles may not be error-free (page 5): "A more realistic view is that we may be replacing at least partially crashes associated with human error by crashes caused by imperfect automated systems in the intermediate stages." The paper goes on to point out that benefits of automated transport in terms of less congestion depends on an increased use of shared transport. It is pointed out that (page 7): "To improve on human drivers, an AD system must typically have a fatal crash rate better than one fatality per billion of kilometres, making testing and verification of performance a difficult or even impossible task."

It is important to remember that not all modes of travel are going to be automated. Thus, FERSI points out (page 9): "Cyclists, pedestrians, motorcycle, and moped riders are not likely to gain immediate benefits from AD or ITS technology." Even if automation technology may ultimately be able to prevent cars from striking pedestrians, the non-automated modes of travel will have crashes between themselves, e.g. motorcycles crashing with pedestrians or cyclists, etc.

FERSI warns against introducing SAE level 3 automated driving (page 11): "As mentioned previously, human limits in staying alert and acting as a fallback when system automation fails may in fact preclude the introduction of level 3 AD systems completely, which would coincide with FERSI's general view."

In short, FERSI sounds a note of caution, and proposes ten principles it believes must be adhered to in order to make sure that vehicle automation will improve road safety. It is outside the scope of this deliverable to discuss these principles in detail; readers are referred to FERSI (2018).

The International Transport Forum (ITF 2018) has published a report entitled: "Safer roads with automated vehicles?" Like the FERSI paper, it sounds a note of caution, but with a different focus than FERSI. Some of the main conclusions listed at the start of the report are worth quoting (page 5): "It seems likely that the number of road crashes will decrease with automation, but crashes will not disappear. ... Vehicle automation strategies that keep humans involved in the driving task seem risky ..., the risk of unintended consequences that would make driving less safe, not more, could increase."

The report notes that programming code for automated driving has been found to contain 20-50 errors per 1000 lines of code, and that only 15 % of the errors are detected by quality checking routines. While not all of these errors may be very serious, they show that automated driving relies on computer software developed and written by fallible humans.

The ITF report devotes 10 pages to discussing the threat of cyber attacks. Although the risk of such attacks is not quantified and may be impossible to quantify in a meaningful way, it is clear that the risk is real and may limit the effectiveness of CATS as well as undermine trust in these systems. Deliverable 3.2 will discuss cyber threats more extensively.

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